

Acknowledgement

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A Rapid method for the gravimetric determination of Copper(II) in presence of Cadmium(II) by α -keto acid oxime

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QUANTITATIVE precipitation of copper by phenylpyruvic acid oxime has been reported by Katyaj and Singh¹. It has been reported by the same authors² that in highly acidic medium (HNO_3) at 1-2 pH cadmium salt gives no precipitate with phenylpyruvic acid oxime and copper complex undergoes partial decomposition and hence separation of copper in presence of cadmium is not possible. It has been observed that in highly acidic medium (H_2SO_4) at pH 1-2 copper ion forms bluish copper complex with phenylpyruvic acid oxime while cadmium ion remains in the solution. By raising the pH of the solution upto 6-7, cadmium is precipitated as $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_2$ but as the complex is slightly soluble, no quantitative precipitation could be obtained and therefore cadmium is estimated as oxinate³.

Experimental

Standard Copper sulphate solution : To prepare the standard solution $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.9824 g.) of B.D.H. (A.R.) grade was dissolved in water, few drops of dilute sulphuric acid was added and the volume made 250 ml. The amount of copper was determined iodometrically⁴.

Standard Cadmium sulphate solution : The standard solution was prepared by dissolving $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (about 2.0 g.) in 250 ml water and cadmium was estimated as cadmium oxinate³ with 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Phenylpyruvic Acid Oxime : Phenylpyruvic acid was prepared from benzaldehyde via azalactone synthesis⁵. The acid (5.0 g.) was converted to its oxime by treating its solution in sodium hydroxide (70 ml, 10%) with aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (6.0 g. in 10 ml). The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and acidified

with hydrochloric acid to give the oxime, crystallising from benzene, m.p. 162°-63°. Hiromoto Ueda and Masaki Ohta⁶ reported its m.p. 160°-62°.

Procedure : A mixture of copper sulphate and cadmium sulphate solutions in different proportions was taken and the pH was adjusted to 1-2 by the addition of dilute sulphuric acid. An ethanolic solution of phenylpyruvic acid oxime (3%) was added to it. Copper was precipitated as copper phenylpyruvic acid oxime while cadmium ion remains in the solution.

The ligand solution was added dropwise till the precipitation was complete. The whole contents were heated on water bath for 15 min and filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible. The precipitate was washed several times with hot water to remove sulphate ion and finally with alcohol to remove the excess of the ligand. It was dried at 110.20° for 45 min in an air oven, cooled in a desiccator and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_2$ to a constant weight.

The filtrate with washings were collected and evaporated to dryness with conc. nitric acid till the residue became colourless (3-4 times required). Finally it was evaporated with dilute nitric acid and the solution was made in water. Cadmium was estimated as cadmium oxinate³ by the help of 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Results

Metals present in mixture in mg		Metals estimated in mg		% Error	
Cu	Cd	Cu	Cd	Cu	Cd
1.0296	100.84	1.0298	101.065	0.02	0.23
		1.0298	101.12	0.02	0.28
5.148	80.672	5.149	80.684	0.02	0.015
		5.119	80.627	0.56	0.055
10.296	60.504	10.268	60.414	0.27	0.15
		10.298	60.471	0.02	0.05
25.739	40.338	25.685	40.314	0.21	0.06
		25.716	40.426	0.09	0.22
51.478	20.168	51.594	20.156	0.23	0.06
		51.618	20.213	0.27	0.22

The above experimental results indicate that even a small amount of copper present in the mixture of copper and cadmium salts solution can be successfully separated and estimated. If the amount of copper or cadmium is varied, the separation and estimation can be done with equal efficiency.

The thermogravimetric study of the complexes shows that both copper and cadmium complexes are quite stable upto 140°.

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Spectrophotometric Studies of Iron(III) complexes with Carboxylic acids using an Auxiliary Complexing Agent

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC studies on complex formation between iron(III) and 2-hydroxy butyrophene (OHB) and 2-hydroxy-4-methylbutyrophene (4MeOHB) have been reported by us earlier^{1,2}. We report now the use of these phenones as an auxiliary ligand in determining the composition of the colourless complexes formed by citric, oxalic, malonic and ethylene diamine tetraacetic acids with iron(III) in acid media.

Experimental

OHB and 4MeOHB were prepared as described earlier^{1,2}. Standard reagent solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of reagent in pure methanol. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality. The stock iron(III) solutions was prepared as shown earlier³. The stock solutions of citric acid, oxalic acid, malonic acid and ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of each in 0.01M HNO₃. Dilute solutions of same acidity but desired concentrations were obtained as and when needed by diluting the stock solution with 0.01M HNO₃. All aqueous solutions were prepared in water twice distilled over alkaline permanganate.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Zeiss-Specol, using 1 cm matched cells. All measurements were carried out at 30° ± 1° in a 50% water—50% methanol (by volume) medium adjusted to 0.005M with respect to nitric acid.

The method used has been described earlier³. A solution containing FeA⁺² (5 × 10⁻⁴M) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of iron(III) (1 × 10⁻³M) and A (1 × 10⁻²M) (A = OHB or 4MeOHB) solutions. The continuous variation⁴ studies were carried out using 5 × 10⁻⁴M FeA⁺² and 5 × 10⁻⁴M carboxylic acid solutions. The absorbances were measured at 530 nm since this is the λ_{max} for both Fe(III)-OHB and Fe(III)-4MeOHB systems^{1,2}.

Two sets of solutions for each equilibrium, one with and the other without the carboxylic acid were prepared. The difference in the absorbances of the pair of corresponding solutions for the two sets corresponds to the Y function in Job's curve. Maximum in Y indicates 1:1 composition for the colourless complexes of iron(III) with citric acid, oxalic acid, malonic acid and EDTA. Typical results are shown in Fig. 1. for Fe(III)-OHB-EDTA system. It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the maximum

Fig. 1. Job's curves in equimolar solutions for the iron (III)-OHB-EDTA system.
Curve A: Fe (III)-OHB
Curve B: Fe(III)-OHB-EDTA
Curve C: Difference of curves A and B.

decolourisation was observed at a ratio of iron(III): EDTA = 1:1. This indicates the formation of a complex correspondingly used. Results obtained with citric acid, oxalic and malonic acids also indicated that iron(III) formed 1:1 complexes with these acids under the conditions of the present study.

In order to find out if mixed ligand complex formation occurred under the conditions of study, the following test was done for each equilibrium studied. To a solution containing iron(III) and excess A, increasing amounts of carboxylic acid were added and the absorbance was measured. The absorbance over the entire visible range was observed to decrease as the concentration of the added carboxylic acid increased. This was interpreted to indicate a progressive conversion of FeA⁺² to Fe-carboxylate complex. It was concluded therefore that no mixed ligand complexes were formed, atleast under the conditions of present study, in these systems.

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